

Project No.: 644606
Project acronym: Photonics4All
Project title: EU-wide outreach for promoting photonics to young people, entrepreneurs and the general public
Instrument: Coordination and Support Action
Programme: ICT-26-2014: Photonics KET
Start date of project: 01.01.2015
Duration: 24 Months

Deliverable 1.2

Competition for the development of a photonics game

Deliverable Name	1 competition for the development of a photonics game
Deliverable Number	D 1.2
Work Package	WP 1 – Outreach for promoting photonics to young people
Associated Task	T 1.2 Photonics for competition
Covered Period	M1-M13
Due Date	M13 (after bilateral consultation between CNR and EC)
Completion Date	M13
Submission Date	M14
Deliverable Lead Partner	CNR
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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

Task 1.2 of the Photonics4All project involves the organization of a photonics competition for High School students. The goal of the competition is the creation of an original board game having photonics and light as the central theme. The participants are asked to submit a ready-to-play game including the rules, the board and all the necessary components.

The task is divided in two main parts:

- a) Organization, promotion and completion of the contest, and use of this activity for fostering interest and awareness on Photonics.
- b) Collection, analysis, sharing and diffusion of experiences and results and identification of a best practice.

The first year of the project has been essentially devoted to part (a), with an activity mainly concentrated on the contest organization and promotion in the country where the competition takes place (Italy), as originally planned.

After the completion of the contest, at the beginning of the second year of the project, the focus will be moved to part (b), with the spread of the results at an international level. This will be pursued by presenting and promoting the competition's experience and the resulting best games in the project meetings and in other European events such as conferences and meetings on Photonics and on games (such as the Photonics21 meeting in March 2016 or the European Conference on Game Based Learning in October 2016).

Moreover, the final award ceremony will be held in conjunction with the "Premio Archimede 2016", a contest for board game designer that, although held in Venice (Italy), is characterized by a strong international dimension, with a large number of international participants, a collaboration with the Swiss "Musée Suisse du Jeu" (Museum of Games), and a jury mainly composed by international experts from the main board-games worldwide companies (Ravensburger, Germany, Hans im Glück, Germany, Asmodee, France, Hasbro, USA, Phalanx, Netherlands, Piatnik, Austria, etc.). All this activity will be finalized in a contribution to the best practice handbook (Task 4.5) and, hopefully, in one or more papers in international journals.

2. Schedule

- Competition start - September 2015
- Pre-registration deadline – December 2015
- Deadline for game submission - January 2016
- Selection of finalists - February - March 2016
- Final and awards ceremony - October 2016

3. Methodology

The general aim of this activity is to use board games and their creation to raise awareness on photonics and light. In fact, by using the competition and its promotion we aim at penetrating different cultural contexts: schools, families and general public. The effectiveness of games as a dissemination tool will be explored and at the end best practices will be identified.

3.1 Competition development

The development of the competition has been articulated in the following actions:

- Development of a dedicated website (www.fotonicaingiochi.it) and Facebook page (www.facebook.com/fotonicaingiochi)
- Definition and publication of the competition rules (www.fotonicaingiochi.it/bando)
- Agreement for a shared award ceremony in occasion of the "Premio Archimede", the main Italian competition for board game designers organized by Studiogiocchi (important Italian board game agency)
- Announcement on newsletters specialized in science outreach, didactics and board games. Some examples:
 - o www.almanacco.cnr.it/reader/cw_usr_view_opportunita.html?id_articolo=7040&giornale=7023
 - o www.dsftm.cnr.it/fotonica-in-gioco-concorso-per-studenti-delle-scuole-secondarie-di-secondo-grado
 - o www.artinmovimento.com/fotonica-in-gioco-un-concorso-sulla-luce-per-gli-studenti
 - o dida.orizzontescuola.it/news/fotonica-gioco-concorso-gli-studenti-delle-scuole-secondarie-di-secondo-grado
- Invitations e-mails sent to Public Italian High Schools offices

3.2 Competition promotion: materials

- Flyer presenting the "Photonics Games" competition
- Quantum Race, a didactical board game on Quantum Mechanics and wave-particle duality (5 tabletop copies)
- Quantum Race, giant version for exhibitions (4.0 m x 2.5 m)
- Roll-up presenting the "Photonics Games" competition
- Roll-up presenting Quantum Race game

3.3 Competition promotion: laboratories and exhibitions

The competition has been promoted in occasion of different Science and Games Festivals around the country with the organization of laboratories and exhibitions.

- Carrara Show, 31 May - 2 June 2015, Carrara, Italy
Games and Comics festival (about 20 000 total presences)
Quantum Race, laboratory/exhibition with the giant board game Quantum Race (about 80 participants)
- European Researcher's Night, 25 September 2015, Rome, Italy
Public Science Event (about 1000 total presences)
Quantum Race, laboratory/exhibition with the giant board game Quantum Race (about 50 participants)
- Le Frontiere della Luce: viaggio alla scoperta della luce estrema, 8 October 2015, Rome, Italy
Public Conference, CNR (Italian National Research Council)
Photonics Games, exhibition/laboratory based on the board game Quantum Race
- Festival della Scienza di Genova, 23 October - 1 November 2015, Genova, Italy
Science festival (about 180 000 total presences)
Fotonica in gioco: le mani in pasta (Photonics Games: hands on), creative laboratory for the design of board games on light (about 650 participants)
- Lucca Comics & Games, 29 October - 1 November 2015, Lucca, Italy
Games and Comics festival (about 200 000 total presences)
Giocare con la Scienza: dalla relatività ai quanti con dadi e pedine (Playing with Science: from relativity to quanta with dices and pawns), laboratory based on the board game Quantum Race (about 250 participants)

3.4 Competition promotion: Public Conferences

The competition has been promoted in occasion of different Science and Games Festivals also with talks for the large public.

- Carrara Show, 31 May 2015, Carrara, Italy
Games and Comics festival
Fotonica in Gioco (Photonics Games)
- 101° Congress of the Italian Physical Society, 24 September 2015, Rome, Italy
Giochi da tavolo come strumento per la didattica: da Quantum Race al concorso Fotonica in Gioco (Board games as learning tools: from Quantum Race to Photonics Games)
- Festival della Scienza di Genova, 26 October 2015, Genova, Italy
Science festival
Fotonica in gioco: inventare giochi per raccontare la luce (Photonics Games: inventing games to narrate the light)
- Lucca Comics & Games, 29 October 2015, Lucca, Italy
Games and Comics festival
Quantum Race: il gioco. Giochi quantistici nell'anno della Luce (Quantum Race: the game. Quantum Games in the International Year of Light)

3.5 International Academic Activities

The competition is accompanied by an academic activity aimed at assessing the effectiveness of the used tools, in particular in view of the definition of indications for the best practices.

- 9th European Conference on Games Based Learning 2015, 8 - 9 October 2015, Steinekjer, Norway
Board Games to Learn Complex Scientific Concepts and the "Photonics Games" Competition, poster presentation
- Proceedings of the 9th European Conference on Games Based Learning 2015
Board Games to Learn Complex Scientific Concepts and the "Photonics Games" Competition, reviewed paper
Published by Academic Conferences and Publishing International Limited Reading, UK
ISBN: 9781910810583 (2015)

The network of contacts developed during the beginning of the project has made available a number of important opportunities for the promotion of the competition and of photonics (invitations to festivals and other events). The exploitation of these opportunities required bigger efforts than foreseen in the Project. In particular, the participation in the conferences, meetings and festivals was crucial to disseminate the competition among possible participants. The results in terms of number of participants (see next section) justify the efforts.

4. Results

4.1 Pre-registered teams

At 31 December 2015 we had 31 pre-registered participants to the competition coming from several different places in Italy and 10 more registrations arrived in January. Most of the pre-registered teams are organised by teachers and a number of them directly by students. It must be considered that the pre-registrations are not binding so that a reduction of the number of effective participants was expected.

The list of the pre-registered team is contained in the following table:

	Name	Role	School	Town
1	Raffaella Pasino	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "B. Pascal"	Abbiategrosso (MI)
2	Alessandro Dell'Aere	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "G. Salvemini"	Bari
3	Elvira Peviani	Teacher	Liceo "G. Novello"	Codogno (LO)
4	Tommaso Marino	Teacher	IIS "M. Curie"	Collegno (TO)
5	Luca Galoppo	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "G. Galilei"	Erba (CO)
6	David Frulla	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Jesi (AN)
7	Manuela Monti	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
8	Manuela Monti	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
9	Ornella Vitiello	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
10	Tania Valente	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
11	Rosaria Di Mambro	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
12	Loredana Colamasi	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
13	Pasquale Cavallo	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
14	Graziana Moretto	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
15	Federico Vilardo	Teacher	Liceo "A. Manzoni"	Latina
16	Luca Fabietti	Teacher	Liceo "E. Majorana"	Latina
17	Luca Fabietti	Teacher	Liceo "E. Majorana"	Latina
18	Luca Fabietti	Teacher	Liceo "E. Majorana"	Latina
19	Gualtiero Grassucci	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "G. B. Grassi"	Latina
20	Giovanna Agostoni	Teacher	Istituto "J. Monnet"	Mariano Comense (CO)
21	Elisabetta D'Alessandro	Teacher	IIS "Galilei-Luxemburg"	Milano
22	Mirella Padoan	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "I. Nievo"	Padova
23	Paola Calvi	Teacher	Liceo Artistico "A. Volta"	Pavia
24	Mario Di Fonza	Teacher	ISIS "Europa"	Pomigliano d'Arco (NA)
25	Matilde Bindi	Teacher	Liceo Linguistico "E. Montale"	Pontedera (PI)
26	Michelangelo Manetta	Teacher	IIS "C. Livì"	Prato
27	Gabriella Gallo	Teacher	IIS "C. Rosatelli"	Rieti
28	Lina Verì	Teacher	Liceo Classico/Linguistico "Aristofane"	Roma
29	Riccardo Chiucchi	Teacher	IIS "Alessandrini-Marino-Forti"	Teramo
30	Massimo Bosetti	Teacher	Istituto di Istruzione "L. Guetti"	Tione (TN)
31	Francesca Chinello	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Treviso
32	Francesca Chinello	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Treviso
33	Patrizia Troncon	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Treviso
34	Patrizia Troncon	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Treviso
35	Gemma Fiorito	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "L. da Vinci"	Treviso
36	Marco	Student	Liceo Scientifico "L. Luana"	Urbino
37	Tommaso Cantoni	Student	Liceo Scientifico "G. Ferraris"	Varese
38	Michela Pavan	Teacher	Liceo Scientifico "G. Ferraris"	Varese
39	Lorenzo Calogero	Student	Liceo Scientifico "F. Juvarra"	Venaria Reale (TO)
40	Cesare Mercalli	Student	Liceo Scientifico "B. Cairoli"	Vigevano (PV)
41	Bianca Maria Pazzi	Student	Liceo Scientifico "B. Cairoli"	Vigevano (PV)

4.2 Submitted games

The deadline for the submission of the games was 31 January 2016. We received 28 games, which amounts to the 68% of the preregistered teams. The overall number of students involved in the competition is 426, with 37 teachers coming from 16 different towns.

	Title of game	Name	Town
1	WHO WANTS TO BE A SCIENTIST?	Raffaella Pasino	Abbiategrosso (MI)
2	Photonics Wars	Sandro Dell'Aere	Bari
3	φως LUCE	Tommaso Marino	Collegno (TO)
4	VICTORY CUBE (V3)	Luca Galoppo	Erba (CO)
5	MARAMA	David Frulla	Jesi (AN)
6	Seven colors games	Manuela Monti	Latina
7	FOTONIX	Manuela Monti	Latina
8	C - The speed of Light	Ornella Vitiello	Latina
9	WIN OR BACK	Tania Valente	Latina
10	COLOUR RACE	Luca Fabietti	Latina
11	LUX MANIA	Luca Fabietti	Latina
12	PIXEL MANIA	Luca Fabietti	Latina
13	Lampo di genio	Gualtiero Grassucci	Latina
14	LIGHTMAZE – Il Gioco della Fotonica	Giovanna Agostoni	Mariano Comense (CO)
15	RIFLETTIAMOci!	Elisabetta D'Alessandro	Milano
16	Quanto è bello!	Paola Calvi	Pavia
17	Light Finder	Mario Di Fonza	Pomigliano d'Arco (NA)
18	FOTO QUIZ	Matilde Bindi	Pontedera (PI)
19	HELIOSCAPE: fuga dal sole	Michelangelo Manetta	Prato
20	Light Box	Massimo Bosetti	Tione (TN)
21	LUX	Francesca Chinello	Treviso
22	NON TI ABBAGLIARE	Francesca Chinello	Treviso
23	Scienziati Fotonici	Patrizia Troncon	Treviso
24	PHOTOLABIRINTO	Patrizia Troncon	Treviso
25	PHOTONIO: indagine ad alta frequenza	Gemma Fiorito	Treviso
26	Rainbow Race	Lorenzo Calogero	Venaria Reale (TO)
27	FOTONIC 2015	Cesare Mercalli	Vigevano (PV)
28	Lumina	Bianca Maria Pazzi	Vigevano (PV)

The following gallery shows some picture of the participating prototypes.

In the map below it is reported the distribution of the participating teams on the Italian territory. We observe a large number of submitted games (about 18) in the neighborhood of the local groups of CNR involved in the Project (Rome, Milan, Trento and Florence), where the direct contact of organizers with schools and teachers has fostered the participation, but also a significant participation from other cities (about 9). Unfortunately, we were not able to reach enough schools in the southern part of Italy.

Source: google maps

4.3 Finalists` selection

The selection of the finalist games will be made by a commission of experts on photonics and board games, immediately after the deadline of the competition with the arrive of the shipped prototypes, presumably during the months of February and March 2016. The commission will select the best three games according to the criteria defined in the competition announcement, which are:

1. Originality of the game mechanisms;
2. Playability;
3. Enjoyment;
4. Proper introduction of issues related to light and photonics;
5. Capacity to illustrate and explain concepts related to the themes of light;
6. Interaction between players;
7. Pertinence of the setting;
8. Quality of the prototype.

4.4 Promotion of the finalist games

Finalist games will be presented (and played) in the context of events, festivals and fairs dedicated to games and light in the period April to October 2016, before and immediately after the final award ceremony.

5. Awards

Each of the three best games will be awarded by a prize of 600 Euros, devolved to the schools of origin with the obligation to be spent as contribution for didactical activities suggested and in favour of the winners' classes. These three best games will be admitted to the final ceremony during the activities of Premio Archimede 2016 where the first, second and third places will be announced and awarded with certificates and trophies.

6. Perspectives

The participation of students to the competition has been enthusiastic and the quality of the presented prototypes looks very high. Moreover, the feedback from teachers is very positive: in many cases the competition has been used from them as a basis to build a wider educational project on light and photonics.

All these elements urge the valorisation of the proposed games (and of the entire experience) at a pan-European level. We could imagine, for instance, to make copies of the best games translated in different languages and to propose them during outreach events all around EU involving Photonics4All partners. In Italy we already have contacts with local events during which we will organize playing sessions for general public involving the teams creating some of the games.

We will disseminate the activity of game creation through Photonics4All newsletter, by posting on social media and by including it in the Photonics4All best practice handbook.

Finally, we include a tentative list of conferences, meetings, festivals during which the activity of game developing and the results of the competition will be presented both to scientific and general public. Where possible, the winning games and other selected games will be shown and played.

Event	Kind of presentation	Place	Date
Photonics21 Annual Meeting	Oral/exhibition	Brussels, Belgium	1-2/3/2016
Italian Meeting on Game Design	Oral	Modena, Italy	1/4/2016
Comicon 2016	Laboratory/exhibition	Napoli, Italy	22-25/4/2016
Festival della Luce-Lake Como	Laboratory/exhibition	Como, Italy	6-11/5/2016
National Congress of Italian Physical Society (SIF)	To be defined	Padova, Italy	21-25/9/2016
European Conference on Game Based Learning (ECGBL 2016)	To be defined	Paisley, Scotland	6-7/10/2016
Festival della Scienza di Genova	To be defined	Genova, Italy	27/10-6/11/2016
Lucca Comics & Games	To be defined	Lucca, Italy	28/10-1/11/2016
Premio Archimede 2016	Award Ceremony	Venezia, Italy	Sept./Oct. 2016